

Effective Public Service Delivery in Madhesh

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Abstract

Service delivery is duty and right raises from taxation either state or province. In Nepal, People pay more tax in comparison of South Asian Countries. Nepal's marginal tax rate of 39%, Bangladesh maxes out at 25% and India at around 30%. Service delivery is too poor in populated Madhes Province districts. General people are treated as servants and officer or Government servants present themselves as owners. Delaying in service delivery has become habit. No WASH facilities, no enough benches or chairs, no disabled friendly service, no consideration of old aged people, no priority of pregnant woman and ladies with infant, no Parking in office premise. If some furniture available that is made of steel or plastic, gets too cold in winter and hot in summer. Service taker (clients) are standing in hot sun. People felt lucky when they get performed needed services on the same day at crowded offices; Hospital, CDO, DPO Land Revenue, Land Reform, Survey, Transport and so on. Except revenue they have to pay extra to get performed their work. The work is not legal when public consult the employee but that is legal when the document is brought by brokers. Either of old persons or disabled persons and pregnant or woman with infant are treated same manner. It is not easy to get service of Voiceless people their own. They need either leader or broker. Observing the situation of the offices it is found. Enhance and Hurdle free Public services on due date and time and attract the Provincial Govt. and Service Provider toward problem. Offices are in grip of brokers. Madhes Province Govt. has raise a slogans for FY-2082-083' Hello C.M.(5.21,5.24) and *Mero Paisa Kaha Janchha* ? This is a step in Good Governance. Link local and Province Govt. and offices digitally. Required Documents should be sent on email and clients should be called on due date. Office within reach of all. Public hearing of all. Enhance Public Service Provider building capacity and updating. Public Survey should be conducted tri-monthly about Govt. Offices service delivery and Provincial Govt. Set up Help desk in crowded offices. Change in behavior, show accountability hassle free public friendly service.

Keywords: taxation, servant, broker, voiceless, people friendly, survey, slogan